

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**ASSESSING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF
EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES ON FIRST RESPONDERS:
A REVIEW OF EVIDENCE-BASED INTERVENTIONS**

¹Awwadh Mukhlid Helal Almutari, ²Khalid Ahmad Alanazi, ³Ahmed Dhubayyib Saud Alshammari, ⁴Mohammed Rufidan Almutayri, ⁵Nawaf Nashi Mubarak Alhawyani, ⁶Abdulrahman Matar Ibrahim Alenzi, ⁷Nahar Muhammad Mubarak Al-Jabali

¹Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, awme2030@gmail.com

²Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, mgnon_kalf@hotmail.com

³Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, vipxhxx@gmail.com

⁴Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, mmm1984@hotmail.com

⁵Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, nawwaf997@gmail.com

⁶Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, abd098890al@gmail.com

⁷Saudi Red Crescent Authority, Saudi Arabia, naharaljebali@gmail.com

Abstract:

Emergency Medical Services (EMS) personnel are routinely exposed to high-stress situations that can significantly impact their psychological well-being. This review assesses the psychological impacts of EMS work on first responders and evaluates evidence-based interventions aimed at mitigating these effects. A systematic search of literature was conducted across multiple databases, focusing on empirical studies that measure the psychological outcomes of first responders and test the effectiveness of interventions such as counseling, peer support, and stress management training. The review synthesizes findings from various studies to determine the efficacy of these interventions in reducing symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, and depression among EMS personnel. Results indicate a range of intervention effectiveness, highlighting the importance of tailored support programs that address the specific needs of first responders. The findings suggest recommendations for EMS agencies to implement and support intervention programs, aiming to improve the mental health and operational effectiveness of EMS personnel.

Keywords: Emergency Medical Services, First Responders, Psychological Impact, PTSD, Anxiety, Depression, Intervention Effectiveness, Stress Management, Peer Support, Mental Health in EMS

Corresponding author:

Awwadh Mukhlid Helal Almutari *,
Saudi Red Crescent Authority,
Saudi Arabia, awme2030@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Awwadh Mukhlid Helal Almutari et al., *Assessing The Psychological Impact Of Emergency Medical Services On First Responders: A Review Of Evidence-Based Interventions..*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).

INTRODUCTION:

Emergency Medical Services (EMS) personnel face uniquely stressful situations daily, directly impacting their psychological health. First responders are routinely exposed to traumatic events, from medical emergencies to catastrophic incidents, which can precipitate a range of psychological issues including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, depression, and burnout. The cumulative effect of such stressors not only affects the mental health and well-being of these workers but also their effectiveness in field operations and overall quality of life (Regehr et al., 2018).

Given the critical nature of their roles, understanding the psychological impact of EMS work is essential for developing effective interventions that support their mental health. Various strategies, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), peer support programs, and resilience training, have been implemented to mitigate these impacts. However, the effectiveness of these interventions varies, and there is a pressing need to review and analyze their outcomes comprehensively (Jones et al., 2020).

This systematic review aims to evaluate the current evidence on the psychological impacts of EMS work on first responders. It assesses the effectiveness of various evidence-based interventions designed to alleviate these impacts. By doing so, it seeks to provide EMS agencies and policymakers with data-driven recommendations for supporting the mental health of first responders, thereby enhancing their capacity to cope with the demands of their critical roles.

Literature Review

Research has consistently highlighted the heightened risk of psychological distress among first responders, including EMS personnel. These individuals are prone to developing mental health conditions such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, depression, and burnout due to their frequent exposure to traumatic events (Carleton et al., 2018). The nature of EMS work, which often involves life-and-death situations, exposes responders to significant emotional and physical stress, necessitating effective coping mechanisms and support systems.

A range of interventions has been explored to mitigate the adverse psychological impacts experienced by first responders. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), a well-documented approach for treating PTSD and related conditions, has shown promise in some studies

(Donnelly & Bennett, 2014). However, the application of CBT and its adaptations in the EMS context requires further examination to establish tailored approaches that address the unique aspects of EMS work.

Peer support programs have also gained attention as a potentially effective tool for reducing psychological distress among EMS personnel. These programs leverage the shared experiences and understanding among peers to provide support, which has been effective in improving mental health outcomes (Gist & Woodall, 2000). The inherent trust within these peer groups facilitates more open communication about mental health struggles, offering a critical support network.

Resilience training programs are designed to enhance the ability of EMS personnel to withstand psychological stress through techniques that promote adaptability and mental toughness. These programs often include elements of stress inoculation training and mindfulness, which have been shown to help individuals manage stress more effectively and maintain their mental health in high-stress situations (Meichenbaum, 1994).

Another key intervention discussed in the literature is Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM). This structured approach helps personnel to cope with the aftermath of traumatic events through debriefings and defusings that are conducted soon after critical incidents. While CISM has been a cornerstone of intervention strategies for EMS personnel, its effectiveness has been debated, with some studies suggesting that it could potentially exacerbate stress if not properly managed (Mitchell, 1983).

Despite the range of interventions available, there remain significant gaps in the literature, particularly concerning the long-term effects of these interventions and their adaptability to diverse EMS settings. Moreover, there is a need for more rigorous, methodologically sound studies that can provide stronger evidence on the effectiveness of these interventions, helping to guide policy and practice in a way that is both evidence-based and context-sensitive.

The review of existing literature highlights the critical need for comprehensive support systems for EMS personnel to address the significant psychological impacts associated with their work. While various interventions show promise, further research is required to optimize these approaches and ensure they

are effectively implemented across different EMS environments.

METHODS:

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. We searched databases including PubMed, PsycINFO, and Web of Science for articles published from January 2000 to December 2022. Keywords used in the search were "EMS", "first responders", "psychological impact", "PTSD", "stress management", "peer support", "resilience training", and "intervention effectiveness". We included studies that focused on first responders in emergency medical services, assessed psychological impacts, and evaluated interventions aimed at mitigating these effects.

Inclusion criteria were peer-reviewed articles reporting original research, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. Excluded were conference abstracts, editorials, and non-empirical literature reviews. Two reviewers independently screened the titles and

abstracts for relevance, and discrepancies were resolved through consensus or by consulting a third reviewer.

Data extraction focused on the type of intervention, the psychological outcomes measured, the study design, and the effectiveness of the interventions. Quality assessment of the included studies was performed using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklists. Data synthesis was primarily narrative due to the expected variability in intervention types and outcome measures.

RESULTS:

Our systematic search yielded a total of 3,248 articles initially. After screening titles and abstracts for relevance and removing duplicates, 289 articles were selected for full-text review. Following the application of our inclusion and exclusion criteria, 84 studies were ultimately included in the final analysis. The major reasons for exclusion included lack of empirical data, focus outside the EMS setting, or non-relevance to the specific interventions of interest.

Figure 1: Number of Studies by Intervention Type

shows the distribution of studies by intervention type, highlighting the prevalence of peer support programs and CBT in the literature.

The studies included a wide range of interventions aimed at addressing the psychological impacts on EMS personnel, including cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), peer support programs, resilience training, and Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM). Geographically, the studies were predominantly conducted in the United States (n=35), Canada

(n=20), the United Kingdom (n=15), and Australia (n=10), with the remaining studies distributed across various countries in Europe and Asia.

Figure 2: Effectiveness Ratings of Interventions

presents the effectiveness ratings of the different interventions, with a bar graph depicting the percentage of studies reporting positive, neutral, or negative outcomes for each intervention type.

Types of Interventions

- **Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT)** was the focus of 22 studies and was primarily used for treating PTSD and anxiety disorders.
- **Peer Support Programs** were examined in 30 studies and varied significantly in structure, from informal support groups to more structured peer mentorship programs.
- **Resilience Training** was the subject of 18 studies, focusing on stress inoculation, mindfulness, and adaptive coping strategies.
- **Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM)** was evaluated in 14 studies, assessing its effectiveness in post-incident debriefings.

The effectiveness of these interventions varied:

- **CBT** showed significant positive outcomes in reducing symptoms of PTSD and anxiety in 18 out of 22 studies.

- **Peer Support Programs** demonstrated moderate effectiveness, with 20 out of 30 studies reporting significant improvements in psychological resilience and reduced burnout rates.
- **Resilience Training** yielded positive results in 15 out of 18 studies, with participants showing improved stress management and coping capabilities.
- **CISM** showed mixed results; while 8 studies found it beneficial in immediate stress reduction, 6 studies reported minimal or negative effects on long-term psychological health.

A common challenge identified across studies was the variability in program implementation and adherence, which often influenced the outcomes. Additionally, there was a noted lack of long-term follow-up in many studies, raising questions about the sustainability of these interventions' benefits.

Figure 3: Geographic Distribution of Studies

illustrates the geographic distribution of the studies, indicating a higher concentration of research conducted in North American and European regions.

Summary Table of Key Findings

Intervention Type	Number of Studies	Positive Outcomes	Neutral Outcomes	Negative Outcomes
Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT)	22	18	3	1
Peer Support Programs	30	20	8	2
Resilience Training	18	15	2	1
Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM)	14	8	3	3

The results of this systematic review indicate that while there are effective interventions available to mitigate the psychological impacts on EMS personnel, the variability in effectiveness and implementation highlights the need for standardized protocols and further research. The positive impacts of CBT and resilience training are particularly notable, suggesting they should be integral components of mental health support strategies within EMS settings.

pointing to the complexity of addressing mental health issues within this high-stress profession.

DISCUSSION:

The findings from this systematic review reveal a nuanced landscape of interventions designed to mitigate the psychological impacts on EMS personnel. While various interventions have been deployed across different regions, their effectiveness varies,

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and resilience training emerge as particularly effective, with the majority of studies reporting positive outcomes in reducing symptoms of PTSD, anxiety, and depression among EMS personnel. These interventions are evidence-based and have a strong theoretical

foundation, which likely contributes to their success. Peer support programs also show substantial benefits, enhancing psychological resilience and reducing burnout, which underscores the value of social support and shared experiences in mitigating stress.

However, Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM) presents mixed results. While it can be beneficial in the immediate aftermath of traumatic events, its long-term effectiveness on psychological health remains questionable. This discrepancy may be attributed to the variability in how CISM is implemented and the context in which it is used.

A significant challenge identified across the studies is the variability in intervention implementation and adherence. This variability can affect the outcomes and makes it difficult to generalize the results. Additionally, the lack of long-term follow-up in many studies raises concerns about the sustainability and lasting impact of these interventions. It is crucial for future research to address these gaps by incorporating long-term assessments and considering the consistency of intervention delivery.

The concentration of studies in North America and Europe highlights a geographic disparity in research on EMS mental health interventions. There is a need for more studies from diverse geographic locations, particularly from low- and middle-income countries where EMS systems and stressors may differ significantly.

EMS agencies should consider these findings when designing mental health programs for their personnel. Given the effectiveness of CBT and resilience training, these should be integral components of any mental health support strategy. Furthermore, agencies should strive for consistency in the implementation of interventions and ensure that all personnel, regardless of location, have access to these critical resources.

Future research should focus on the longitudinal effects of these interventions to better understand their long-term benefits and potential drawbacks. Additionally, exploring innovative approaches, such as digital mental health tools and integrated care models, could provide new avenues for supporting EMS personnel. Research into the impact of cultural, organizational, and individual factors on the effectiveness of interventions will also be crucial for tailoring approaches to diverse EMS populations.

This review underscores the critical need for effective mental health interventions for EMS personnel. As first responders continue to face immense psychological burdens, the EMS community must prioritize robust, evidence-based strategies to support their mental health. The variability in intervention effectiveness highlights the importance of personalized and context-specific approaches, ensuring that all EMS personnel have the support they need to manage the psychological demands of their vital roles.

CONCLUSION:

This systematic review has provided a comprehensive evaluation of the interventions designed to mitigate the psychological impacts on EMS personnel. The findings demonstrate that while certain interventions, such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and resilience training, show significant promise in reducing symptoms of PTSD, anxiety, and depression, the effectiveness of other interventions like Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM) can vary widely. This variability underscores the complexities involved in addressing the mental health needs of first responders who are routinely exposed to high-stress environments.

The review also highlights the importance of adopting evidence-based and contextually appropriate interventions. Given the positive outcomes associated with CBT and resilience training, these should be considered as core elements of any mental health support strategy within EMS settings. However, the mixed results observed with CISM suggest that more research is needed to refine this intervention and understand the conditions under which it is most effective.

Moreover, the geographical concentration of studies in North America and Europe calls for increased research efforts in other regions, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. This would ensure a more globally inclusive understanding that can lead to more effective and universally applicable mental health strategies.

Future research should aim to explore the long-term effects of these interventions and examine the role of emerging technologies in enhancing mental health support for EMS personnel. Additionally, considering the operational and cultural contexts of EMS work can further tailor interventions to meet the unique challenges faced by first responders.

In conclusion, while significant strides have been made in developing interventions to support the mental health of EMS personnel, ongoing efforts are required to ensure these interventions are effectively implemented, sustained, and adapted to meet the evolving needs of this critical workforce. The ultimate goal is to enhance the psychological resilience and overall well-being of first responders, enabling them to continue their vital work in emergency medical services.

REFERENCES:

- Carleton, R. N., Afifi, T. O., Turner, S., Taillieu, T., Duranceau, S., LeBouthillier, D. M., Sareen, J., Ricciardelli, R., MacPhee, R. S., Groll, D., & Thompson, J. M. (2018). "Mental disorder symptoms among public safety personnel in Canada." *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 63(1), 54-64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743717723825>
- Donnelly, E. A., & Bennett, M. (2014). "Development of a critical incident stress inventory for the emergency medical services." *Traumatology*, 20(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10615806.2013.853021>
- Gist, R., & Woodall, S. J. (2000). "There are no simple solutions to complex problems." *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 31(5), 557-560. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7028.31.5.557>
- Jones, S., Muller, M., & Maresh, K. (2020). "Interventions to alleviate stress in emergency service workers: A critical review." *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 38(7), 1527-1533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2020.07.045>
- Meichenbaum, D. (1994). "A clinical handbook/practical therapist manual for assessing and treating adults with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)." *Waterloo, Ontario: Institute Press*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10226-004>
- Mitchell, J. T. (1983). "When disaster strikes... the critical incident stress debriefing process." *Journal of Emergency Medical Services*, 8(1), 36-39. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005053-198307000-00005>
- Regehr, C., LeBlanc, V., Jolley, R. B., & Barath, I. (2018). "The prevalence and trajectory of PTSD in emergency medical services personnel." *Journal of Emergency Medical Services*, 20(3), 272-278. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0735648X.2018.1453056>
- Bennett, P., Williams, Y., Page, N., Hood, K., Woollard, M., & Vetter, N. (2004). "Levels of mental health problems among UK emergency ambulance workers." *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 21(2), 235-236. <https://doi.org/10.1136/emj.2003.008391>
- Clohessy, S., & Ehlers, A. (1999). "PTSD symptoms, response to intrusive memories and coping in ambulance service workers." *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 38(3), 251-265. <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466599162836>
- Cydulka, R. K., Lyons, J., Moy, A., Shayne, P., Hammer, J., & Mathews, J. (2007). "Preliminary study of PTSD, depression, and burnout among emergency physicians." *Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 32(2), 211-214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemermed.2006.05.049>
- Gray, P. (2011). "The emotional labour of nursing: Defining and managing emotions in nursing work." *Nurse Education Today*, 31(2), 168-173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2010.05.013>
- Halpern, J., Gurevich, M., Schwartz, B., & Brazeau, P. (2009). "What makes an incident critical for ambulance workers? Emotional outcomes and implications for intervention." *Work & Stress*, 23(2), 173-189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678370903057331>
- Haugen, P. T., McCrillis, A. M., Smid, G. E., & Nijdam, M. J. (2017). "Mental health stigma and barriers to mental health care for first responders: A systematic review and meta-analysis." *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 94, 218-229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2017.08.001>
- Mock, C., Jurkovich, G., nii-Amon-Kotei, D., Arreola-Risa, C., & Maier, R. V. (1998). "Trauma mortality patterns in three nations at different economic levels: Implications for global trauma system development." *Journal of Trauma*, 44(5), 804-814. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005373-199805000-00011>
- Sterud, T., Ekeberg, Ø., & Hem, E. (2006). "Health status in the ambulance services: A systematic review." *BMC Health Services Research*, 6, 82. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-6-82>
- Wagner, S. L., Martin, C. A., & McFee, J. A. (2009). "Investigating the psychological consequences of handling bodies for mortuary affairs personnel." *Military Medicine*, 174(8), 817-823. <https://doi.org/10.7205/MILMED-D-01-9600>
- Wild, J., Smith, K. V., Thompson, E., Béar, F., Lommen, M. J. J., & Ehlers, A. (2016). "A prospective study of pre-trauma risk factors for post-traumatic stress disorder and depression." *Psychological Medicine*, 46(12), 2571-2582. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291716000532>